

Polarographic Determination of Stability Constants of Cadmium and Lead Ternary Complexes with Thiosemicarbazide and Thiosulphate

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The stability constants of binary and ternary complexes of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions with thiosemicarbazide (TSC) as a primary ligand and thiosulphate (TS) as a secondary ligand have been determined polarographically at 25° and $\mu=0.13$ (M NaNO_3). Cadmium and lead ions individually form 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes with both the ligands. The complexation constants of the mixed species $\beta_{1,1}$, $\beta_{1,2}$ and $\beta_{2,1}$ are calculated. The negative value of $\beta_{1,1}$ in the Pb^{II} -TSC-TS system indicates the absence of $\text{Pb}(\text{TSC})(\text{TS})_2^{\text{II}}$.

THE polarographic behaviour of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in thiosulphate¹⁻⁴ and thiosemicarbazide⁵⁻⁷ solutions has been investigated previously. The mixed complexes of Cd^{II} with thiosulphate as primary ligand were also investigated polarographically^{4,6,8}. The present study of mixed ligand (thiosemicarbazide and thiosulphate) complexes with Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} has been initiated, for which no reference could be traced out in the literature. The composition and stability constants of the complexes formed are studied by polarographic technique.

Experimental

Cadmium nitrate, lead nitrate, sodium thiosulphate, thiosemicarbazide were of reagent grade. The solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. Sodium nitrate was used to adjust the ionic strength at 0.13 M . 0.1% Triton-X100 was used as a maximum suppressor. The concentration of the metal ion (Pb^{II} or Cd^{II}) was fixed at $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ in the polarographic cell.

PRG 3 Polarograph (3-electrode) in conjunction with Tipol plug in and EPL 1 recorder (Tacussel, France) was used to record all the polarograms. The dropping mercury electrode, when inserted into a solution containing 0.1 M NaNO_3 , had a drop time of 3.0 sec per drop and a flow rate of 1.28 mg sec^{-1} of mercury at a column height of 50 cm (open circuit).

Procedure: Deoxygenation of the solution to be polarographed was achieved using purified nitrogen. Four series of solutions of 0.5mM metal ion (Pb^{II} or Cd^{II}) with various amounts of the ligand (thiosulphate or thiosemicarbazide) and the requisite amount of NaNO_3 were polarographed at 25° .

Another series of solutions of 0.5mM metal ion in presence of two different concentrations of thiosulphate (as a secondary ligand), viz. 0.01 and

0.043M with various amounts of thiosemicarbazide (as a primary ligand) were polarographed.

Results and Discussion

Single ligand system: Simple systems of Cd^{II} thiosulphate⁴, Cd^{II} thiosemicarbazide^{6,8}, Pb^{II} thiosulphate⁸ and Pb^{II} thiosemicarbazide⁷ were investigated in order to obtain their stabilities under identical experimental conditions maintained for Cd^{II} or Pb^{II} -thiosemicarbazide-thiosulphate mixed systems.

A single wave was observed in each case. All the plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs E yielded straight lines with slopes, which agree with the theoretical value corresponding to $n=2$ for Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} simple systems. The mean values of the slopes for Pb^{II} - and Cd^{II} -thiosulphate systems are 0.031 and 0.034, respectively. For the thiosemicarbazide systems the mean values of the slopes are 0.030 and 0.029 in the respective order. It is concluded that Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} are reversibly reduced in both thiosulphate and thiosemicarbazide solutions.

With increase in ligand concentration, $E_{1/2}$ values shift to more negative potentials, showing complex formation. The relation between $\log$ ligand concentration and $E_{1/2}$ for each system is curved as indicated by Pb^{II} - and Cd^{II} -thiosemicarbazide systems shown in Fig. 1. The $\log \beta_1$, β_2 and β_3 values obtained by the Deford and Hume treatment¹⁰ are reported in Table 1. Our values are in close agreement with those previously reported by other workers^{3,4,6,7} taking into consideration the differences in the experimental conditions. Differences, however, are noticed between our results and those reported by Goddard *et al.*^{6,7} concerning the Pb^{II} - and Cd^{II} -thiosemicarbazide complexes. Those authors reported that Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} gave 1 : 1

Fig. 1. Plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log [TSC]$ for (x) Cd^{II} and (●) Pb^{II} mixed complexes : (a) 0.0, (b) 0.01 and (c) 0.043 M [TS].

Fig. 2. Distribution of different Cd^{II} -thiosemicarbazide complex species.

TABLE I—LOG FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LEAD AND CADMIUM WITH THIOSULPHATE AND THIOSEMICARBAZIDE

$\mu = 0.13$, $Tem. = 25^\circ$

System	β_1	β_2	β^3
Cd^{II} -Thiosemicarbazide	2.94	3.93	5.66
Cd^{II} -Thiosulphate	2.90	4.80	5.21
Pb^{II} -Thiosemicarbazide	1.95	2.32	3.35
Pb^{II} -Thiosulphate	2.90	5.47	6.65

and 1 : 2 metal to ligand thiosemicarbazide complexes, respectively. The distributions of various binary complexes (simple) in solutions were not reported earlier. Therefore, the distribution diagrams are illustrated in Figs. 2-5.

Fig. 3. Distribution of different Pb^{II} -thiosemicarbazide complex species.

Fig. 4. Distribution of different Cd^{II}-thiosulphate complex species

Mixed ligand system : The Cd^{II}-TSC-TS and Pb^{II}-TSC-TS systems were studied by keeping the concentration of thiosulphate constant at 0.01 and 0.043 M, while varying the concentration of thiosemicarbazide in each case from 2 × 10⁻³ to 0.04 M and at μ = 0.13 M (NaNO₃) in the case of 0.01 M thiosulphate. In all cases, the single well defined and diffusion-controlled wave had a slope of 30 ± 3 mV for the plots of log i/(i_d - i) vs E indicating that the reduction is reversible and involves two electrons.

In each of the mixed system, a shift in the half-wave potential to more negative value with increase in the thiosemicarbazide concentration was observed. The magnitude of this shift being greater in the presence of thiosemicarbazide than that obtained for the simple metal-thiosulphate systems as can be seen from Fig. 1. This shift indicates the formation of mixed ligand complexes with thiosemicarbazide and thiosulphate ion.

Following the method of Schaap and McMasters¹¹ which is an extension of DeFord and Hume¹⁰ treatment of the polarographic data, the functions F₀₀, F₁₀, F₂₀ and F₃₀ set of values for A, B, C and D

Fig. 5. Distribution of different Pb^{II}-thiosulphate complex species.

were obtained for each of the systems. The stability constants calculated from the constants A, B, C and D are cited in Table 2.

The determination of the composition and the evaluation of stability constants of the mixed ligand complexes show that there is a positive replacement of thiosulphate ion by thiosemicarbazide in both the systems. Furthermore, the value of coefficient D which coincides with the stability constant β₂₀ for each system, viz. [Cd(TSC)₂]²⁺ and [Pb(TSC)₂]²⁺ complexes reveals the positive replacement. However, [in the lead mixed systems the value of log β₁₂ is negative indicating the absence of the complex Pb(ISC)(TS)₂²⁻ in solution.

For a comparison of the stabilities of simple and mixed complexes, it is convenient to evaluate the mixing constant, K_m (equilibrium constant) for the reactions¹²,

where, M = Cd^{II} or Pb^{II}. The value of K_m indicates the relative stability of the mixed complex in solution as compared to the parent binary complexes. This is given by the relation,

$$K_m = \beta_{11} / \sqrt{\beta_{02}\beta_{20}}$$

TABLE 2—MIXED FORMATION CONSTANTS
μ = 0.13, Temp. = 25°

System	log A	log B	log C	log D	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
Cd^{II}-Thiosemicarbazide-thiosulphate							
(a) 0.010 M thiosulphate	1.05	4.15	5.25	—	5.91	7.79	7.03
(b) 0.043 M thiosulphate	1.98	5.16	5.19	5.66	—	—	—
Pb^{II}-Thiosemicarbazide-thiosulphate							
(a) 0.010 M thiosulphate	1.62	3.07	4.23	—	—	—	—
(b) 0.043 M thiosulphate	2.64	3.22	4.52	—	5.11	—	6.09

Hence, $\log K_m$ are 1.73 and 1.22 for the Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complex species, respectively. Positive values of mixing constants show that the mixed complex (here, 1 : 1 : 1) is more stable than the simple bis-complexes.

References

1. M. E. MACOVSHI, *Rev. Roum. Chem.*, 1971, **16**, 417.
2. S. C. SARAIYA and A. K. SUNDARAM, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1969, **70**, 120.
3. M. GHANDOUR, A. HAMZA and M. EL-NAJJAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 933.
4. P. D. JADHAV and R. A. BHOBE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 853.
5. V. F. TOROPOVA and K. V. NAIMUSHINA, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1960, **5**, 421.
6. D. R. GODDARD, B. D. LODAM, S. O. AJAYI and M. J. CAMPBELL, *J. Chem. Soc (A)*, 1969, 506.
7. O. S. AJAYI, D. R. GODDARD and J. DANIDK, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, **17**, 1751.
8. P. D. JADHAV and K. A. BHOBE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2290.
9. P. D. JADHAV, R. G. BIDKAR, D. G. DHURBY and R. A. BHOBE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1437.
10. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.
11. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. McMASTERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.
12. S. L. JAIN, J. KISHAN and K. C. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 133.